

Analysis and Experimentation of Interleaved Boost Converter with Ripple Steering for Power Factor Correction

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Abstract : Through the fast growing technologies, design of power factor correction (PFC) circuit is facing several challenges. In this paper, a two-phase interleaved boost converter with ripple steering technique is proposed. Among the various topologies, Interleaved Boost converter (IBC) is considered as superior due to enriched performance, lower ripple content, compact weight and size. A thorough investigation is presented here for the proposed topology. Simulation study for the IBC has been carried out using MATLAB/SIMULINK. Theoretical analysis and hardware prototype has been performed to validate the results.

Keywords : Interleaved Boost Converter (IBC), Power Factor Correction (PFC), Ripple Steering Technique, Ripple, and Simulation.

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